

Plant host range of the rice bug *Leptocorisa oratorius*

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Rice bug (RB) *Leptocorisa oratorius* (Fabricius) comprises 80% of the *Leptocorisa* collections from wetland and dryland rice in the Philippines. *L. acuta* (Thunberg) and *L. palawanensis* Ahmad also are found in significant numbers. Only plants in the milk or dough stage are nutritionally acceptable to *L. oratorius*.

It survives by being long-lived (adults can live over 3 months) and dispersive, seeking late maturing rice or alternative grassy weed hosts.

We studied RB survival on rice and some commonly reported weed hosts. Neonate nymphs were placed on ripening-stage rice and eight common weeds. All nymphs died on *Eleusine indica* (L.) Gaertn., *Paspalum conjugatum* Berg., and *Dactyloctenium aegyptium* (L.) Beauv (see table). *Oryza sativa* L. was the most suitable host, with the most favorable growth index, greatest fecundity, and highest number of stylet sheaths. *Echinochloa* species, led by *E. colona* (L.) Link, were acceptable hosts, but with significantly lower growth indices, fecundity, and number of stylet sheaths. Nymphal development ranged from 21 d with rice to 36 d with *Paspalum scrobiculatum* L. *Paspalidium flavidum* (Retz.) A. Camus and *P. scrobiculatum* can be considered marginal hosts.

Growth and development of <i>L. oratorius</i> on rice and common ricefield grassy weeds.				
IRRI green-house, 1986. ^a/				
Plant ^b /	Growth index ^c /	Insect dry weight (mg)	Fecundity (eggs/female)	Stylet sheaths (no./panicle)
<i>Oryza sativa</i>	1.9a	18a	65a	1.3a
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	1.1b	14ab	51b	1.2ab
<i>E. glabrescens</i> Monro ex Hook f.	0.9c	12b	47bc	1.2ab
<i>E. crus-galli</i> ssp. <i>hispidula</i> (Retz.) Honda	0.9c	12b	45c	1.2ab
<i>Paspalidium flavidum</i>	0.4d	8b	21d	0.7b
<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i>	0.2e	3c	5e	0.5c
^a / Av of 4 replications, 10 rice bugs/5 panicles. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^b / Nymphs failed to develop on <i>Eleusine indica</i> , <i>Paspalum conjugatum</i> , and <i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i> .				
^c Growth index = survival (%) / developmental period (days).				

